

Synthesis of 3-amino-4,5-dihydro(5H)4-oxothieno[3,2-c]quinoline-2-carboxylic acids and their alkyl esters

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Abstract : 4-Hydroxyquinolin-2(H)ones are converted to 4-chloro-3-cyanoquinolin-2(H)ones and are cyclised with thioglycolic acid and its alkyl esters to furnish the title compounds viz. 3-amino-4,5-dihydro(5H)4-oxothieno[3,2-c]quinoline-2-carboxylic acids and their corresponding alkyl esters, which are characterised by elemental analysis and spectral data.

Keywords : Quinolone antibacterials, 4-chloro-3-cyanoquinolin-2(H)ones, oxothieno[3,2-c]quinolones, thioglycolic acid.

Introduction

Recently, the quinolone antibacterials¹⁻³ have emerged as an area of intense interest because of their broad spectrum of activity *in vitro* and *in vivo* chemotherapeutic efficacy. Several quinolones have already been marketed, e.g. norfloxacin, ofloxacin and ciprofloxacin. The success of these compounds has caused an increase in efforts to produce more efficacious and less toxic antibacterial agents. 3,4-Heteroannulated quinolin-2-ones⁴⁻¹¹ are of recent origin and found to be associated with variety of pharmacological properties^{12,13}. Discovery of antibacterial, antipyretic, antimalarial, antihistaminic, antiamebic activities increased current interest in the chemistry of these heterocycles and led to the discovery of various novel quinolones. This observation prompted us to report the present communication.

Results and discussion

4-Hydroxyquinolin-2(H)ones (1a-c) are formylated to the respective 3-formyl-4-hydroxyquinolin-2(H)ones (2a-c), by Riemer-Tiemann reaction¹⁶ which are then converted to the corresponding 3-cyano-4-hydroxyquinolin-2(H)ones (3a-c)^{14,15}. Compounds 3a-c are finally treated with POCl₃ to give 3-cyano-4-chloroquinolin-2(H)ones (4a-c) whose structures have been supported by spectral data (Scheme 1, Table 1). These compounds 4a-c are highly reactive, and readily underwent cyclisation

with thioglycolic acid and its alkyl esters 5a-c furnishing 3-amino-4,5-dihydro(5H)4-oxothieno[3,2-c]quinoline-2-carboxylic acids and their alkyl esters (6a-i, Scheme 2), which are characterised by their elemental analysis and spectral data (Tables 2 and 3). As an illustrative example, 1-methyl-4-chloro-3-cyanoquinolin-2-one (4a) is reacted with ethylthioglycolate (5b) in refluxing dry ethanol in the presence of anhydrous sodium carbonate. Within few minutes silky needles of ethyl 3-amino, 4,5-dihydro-5-methyl-4-oxothieno[3,2-c]quinoline-2-carboxylate (6b) were separated out. IR (KBr) spectrum of 6b revealed the presence of N-C=O (1625 cm⁻¹), O-C=O (1680 cm⁻¹) and -NH₂ (3400 cm⁻¹, doublet) groups. Its ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) spectrum displayed signals at δ 1.37 (3H, t, CH₂-CH₃), 3.69 (3H, s, N-CH₃), 4.32 (2H, q, O-CH₂-CH₃), 7.12 (2H, s, D₂O exchangeable, NH₂), 7.25-7.8 (4H, m, arom). Mass spectrum recorded the molecular ion at *m/z* 302 (M⁺100%) and a M+2 peak at *m/z* 304 (4%) confirmed the presence of sulphur. The decoupled ¹³C NMR spectrum of 6b manifested the presence of 14 carbons. Its corresponding off-resonance spectrum has shown that 7 carbons are protonated and the rest are tertiary in nature. The two singlets in the downfield region at δ 159.4 and 164.3 are assigned to carbonyl carbon of ester group and carbonyl carbon of amide group (C-4) respectively. The singlet at δ 118.2 is assigned to two

Scheme 1

Table 1. Characterisation data of compounds 4a-c

Product	R	Reaction time (h)	Yield (%)	M.p. ^a (°C)	IR (KBr) (cm ⁻¹) N-C=O; -C≡N	¹ H NMR (CDCl ₃ /TMS) δ ppm	MS m/z (M ⁺)
4a	CH ₃	10	60	200-222	1640, 2250	3.80 (3H, s, N-CH ₃), 7.0-7.9 (3H, m, arom), 8.1 (1H, dd, arom, C ⁵ -H)	218
4b	C ₂ H ₅	12	55	196-198	1625, 2250	1.3 (3H, t, CH ₂ -CH ₃), 4.2 (2H, q, CH ₂ -CH ₃), 7.1-7.9 (3H, m, arom), 8.0 (1H, dd, arom, C ⁵ -H)	232
4c	Ph	24	50	236-238	1620, 2200	6.6 (1H, dd, arom, C ⁸ -H), 7.2-7.9 (7H, m, arom), 8.1 (1H, dd, arom, C ⁵ -H)	280

carbons viz. C-2 and C-3a (Table 2). The reaction is considered to proceed through the intermediate 7 (Scheme 2). The nucleophilic addition of the carbanion 7 to the cyano group at position 3 leads to the formation of the final compounds 6a-i.

The reaction has been extended to synthesise nine substituted 3-amino-4,5-dihydro(5H)4-oxothieno[3,2-c]quinoline-2-carboxylic acids and their alkyl esters (6a-i, Scheme 2) whose physical and spectral data are presented

in Tables 2 and 3. The mass fragmentation pattern in all these compounds 6a-i is found to be similar and consistent with the structures assigned.

The title compounds are screened for antibacterial activity by employing paper disc method. The bacterial strains used are *Staphylococcus aureus* (gram +ve) and *Escherichia coli* (gram -ve). The substituted 4,5-dihydro-4-oxothieno[3,2-c]quinolines revealed considerably good antibacterial activity against the bacterial strains. Of them, 3-amino-4,5-dihydro-5-ethyl-4-oxothieno[3,2-c]quinoline-

Scheme 2

Table 2. ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃/TMS) data of compounds 6a, 6b and 6f

Compd.	δ ppm (assignments), J in Hz
6a	28.51 (C-3'), 51.12 (C-2'), 115.15 (C-6), 117.43 (C-9a), 118.13 (C-2 and C-3a), 122.69 (C-8), 124.29 (C-9), 130.89 (C-7), 138.07 (C-9b), 148.81 (C-5a), 153.63 (C-3), 159.55 (C-1'), 164.78 (C-4)
6b	14.58 (q, J 50.2, C-3'), 28.79 (q, J 87.5, C-4'), 60.21 (t, J 100.4, C-2'), 115.17 (d, J 125.5, C-6), 117.50 (s, C-9a), 118.21 (s, C-2 and C-3a), 122.69 (d, J 133.8, C-8), 124.27 (d, J 125.5, C-9), 130.81 (d, J 125.5, C-7), 138.02 (s, C-9b), 148.61 (s, C-5a), 153.39 (s, C-3), 159.47 (s, C-1'), 164.37 (s, C-4)
6f	14.40 (C-3'), 60.22 (C-2'), 117.25 (C-6), 117.49 (C-9a), 118.51 (C-2 and C-3a), 123.15 (C-8), 124.14 (C-9), 128.85 (C-9'), 128.96 (C-7'), 129.26 (8' and C-6'), 130.44 (C-7), 130.59 (C-5'), 137.16 (C-4'), 139.35 (C-9b), 149.59 (C-5a), 153.74 (C-3), 159.93 (C-1'), 164.59 (C-4)

2-carboxylic acid (6h) exhibited most promising antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* at 4 μg/ml concentration and against *E. coli* at 200 μg/ml concentration.

In conclusion the present route provides a facile synthesis of 2,3-disubstituted 4-oxothieno[3,2-*c*]quinolines (6a-i) with good yields. These bifunctional compounds possess good antibacterial activity and further attract increasing attention of organic chemists as synthons.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Melting points are uncorrected and are determined in electrical melting point apparatus. The infrared spectra were obtained in KBr disc on Shimadzu 435 instrument. The proton magnetic resonance spectra were recorded on

Table 3. Characterisation data of compounds 6a-i

Product	Reaction time (min)	Yield (%)	M.p. ^a (°C)	Molecular formula ^b	IR (KBr) (cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (CDCl ₃ /TMS) δ ppm	MS m/z (M ⁺)
6a	15	95	210–212	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	1630, 1680, 3400	3.75 (3H, s, N-CH ₃), 3.94 (3H, s, O-CH ₃), 7.1 (2H, s, exchangeable with D ₂ O, NH ₂), 7.25–7.8 (4H, m, arom)	288 (M ⁺ 100), 256 (40), 230 (40), 228 (40)
6b	15	90	200–201	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ S	1625, 1680, 3400	1.37 (3H, t, J 7.5, O-CH ₂ -CH ₃), 3.69 (3H, s, N-CH ₃), 4.31 (2H, q, J 7.5, O-CH ₂ -CH ₃), 7.12 (2H, s, exchangeable with D ₂ O, NH ₂), 7.25–7.8 (4H, m, arom)	302 (M ⁺ 100), 274 (40), 256 (55), 230 (90)
6c	15	80	233–235	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ S	1630, 1690, 3450	1.2 (3H, t, J 7.2, N-CH ₂ -CH ₃), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.2 (2H, q, J 7.2, N-CH ₂ -CH ₃), 6.93 (2H, s, exchangeable with D ₂ O, NH ₂), 7–7.7 (4H, m, arom)	302 (M ⁺ 100), 270 (60), 244 (50), 242 (20)
6d	45	90	185–188	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	1625, 1685, 3400	1.37 (3H, t, J 7.3, N-CH ₂ -CH ₃), 1.4 (3H, t, J 7.5, O-CH ₂ -CH ₃), 4.32 (2H, q, J 7.3, N-CH ₂ -CH ₃), 4.37 (2H, q, J 7.5, O-CH ₂ -CH ₃), 7.14 (2H, s, exchangeable with D ₂ O, NH ₂), 7.15–7.83 (4H, m, arom)	316 (M ⁺ 100), 288 (40), 270 (50), 244 (30)
6e	5	85	276–278	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₃ S	1615, 1665, 3450	4.0 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.7 (1H, dd, arom C ⁶ -H), 7.0 (2H, s, exchangeable with D ₂ O, NH ₂), 7.1–7.8 (8H, m, arom)	350 (M ⁺ 100), 318 (50), 292 (40), 275 (10)
6f	30	95	231–233	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ S	1610, 1660, 3450	1.37 (3H, t, J 7.6, -OCH ₂ -CH ₃), 4.31 (2H, q, J 7.6, -O-CH ₂ -CH ₃), 6.59 (1H, dd, arom C ⁶ -H), 7.1 (2H, s, exchangeable with D ₂ O, NH ₂), 7.2–7.85 (8H, m, arom)	364 (M ⁺ 10), 336 (2), 318 (20), 292 (60)
6g	5	75	238–240	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ S		Converted into its methylester and characterised as 6a	274 (M ⁺ 10), 230 (40), 201 (5), 185 (5)

Table-3 (contd.)

6h	20	70	250-252	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	Converted into its methylester and characterised as 6c	288 (M ⁺ 10), 270 (15), 244 (30), 242 (10)
6i	30	70	279-280	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ S	Converted into its methylester and characterised as 6e	336 (M ⁺ 10), 318 (40)

^aUncorrected, measured with an electrically heated apparatus.

^bSatisfactory microanalysis obtained C±0.23; H±0.14; N±0.30.

Brüker 300 MHz spectrophotometer with TMS as the internal standard and the ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in the same instrument and the chemical shifts were measured with δ(TMS) = δ(CDCl₃) + 76.9 ppm. The chemical shift values are given in ppm (δ) and coupling constants in Hertz. The mass spectra were recorded on VG-Micro Mass 7070H instrument of direct inlet probe.

4-Chloro-3-cyanoquinolin-2(1*H*)ones (4a-c) :

General procedure : A solution of 4-hydroxy-3-cyanoquinolin-2(1*H*)ones (3a-c)¹⁴⁻¹⁶ (1 mmol) in POCl₃ (5 ml) was refluxed for 20-24 h. The excess solvent was distilled off and the reaction mixture was poured onto crushed ice (100 g). The separated compound was filtered and chromatographed over silica gel (finer than 200 mesh) column, using petroleum ether : benzene 1 : 1 solution as eluent (yield 50-60%).

Alkyl 3-amino-4,5-dihydro(5*H*)4-oxothieno[3,2-*c*]quinoline-2-carboxylates (6a-f) :

General procedure : To a solution of appropriate 4-chloro-3-cyanoquinolin-2(1*H*)one (4a-c, 1 mmol) in absolute alcohol (10 ml), anhydrous Na₂CO₃ (0.106 g, 1 mmol) and alkyl thioglycolate (5a,b, 1 mmol) were added. After refluxing for 15 min yellow silky needles separated from reaction mixture under hot condition. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The resulting solid was suspended in water (50 ml) and stirred for 30 min. The insoluble organic compound 6a-f were filtered, dried and recrystallised from benzene (yield 80-95%).

3-Amino-4,5-dihydro(5*H*)4-oxothieno[3,2-*c*]quinoline-2-carboxylic acids (6g-i) :

General procedure : To a solution of 4-chloro-3-cyanoquinolin-2(1*H*)ones (4a-c, 1 mmol) in absolute etha-

nol (10 ml), anhydrous Na₂CO₃ (0.16 g, 1 mmol) and thioglycolic acid (5c, 0.92 g, 1 mmol) were added and refluxed for 5 to 30 min. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. The solid obtained was dissolved in water (20 ml) and the solution was filtered. The filtrate was cautiously neutralized with dil. HCl to pH 5 and extracted with ethylacetate (30 ml, 3 portions). The combined extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated. The compounds 6g-i that separated were filtered and purified by dissolving in Na₂CO₃ solution (5%) and regenerating by HCl (yield 70-75%).

3-Amino-4,5-dihydro(5*H*)4-oxothieno[3,2-*c*]quinoline-2-carboxylic acids (6g-i) were converted into their corresponding methyl esters (6a,c,e) by dissolving acids (6g-i) in thionylchloride and stirring with methanol for 1 h at room temperature. The solvent was distilled off, under vacuum and the resulting solid was washed with Na₂CO₃ solution (5%) and dried. Compounds 6a, c and e thus obtained were recrystallised from benzene.

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